

Farmer Involvement in Farmer-to-Farmer Innovation Dissemination among Cassava Farmers: Implication for Agricultural Development in Osun State, Nigeria

¹ALEEM Bakare Akande and ²AYINDE Julius Olatunde

Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria
Corresponding Author Email: aleemakandebakare@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Despite innovation being developed in a variety of research stations and other research-generating entities around the country, the extension-to-farmer ratio remains low. Hence, this research was designed to assess farmer involvement in the spread of innovations among Osun State's cassava farmers. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 319 registered cassava farmers in Osun state. Data were collected through a well-structured interview schedule. The analytical tools include Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, frequencies, and percentages. The results show that the mean age was 47.69 ± 10.40 and about (68.0%) were male. Furthermore, the mean income was ₦473,981.19 \pm 201, with farming experience of 15.81 ± 8.48 years. The majority (70.5%) of the farmers indicated moderate involvement in innovation dissemination. The correlation analysis revealed that household size ($r = 0.162$; $p \leq 0.05$), years in formal education ($r = 0.214$; $p \leq 0.05$), estimated annual income ($r = 0.231$; $p \leq 0.01$) and years in cassava farming experience ($r = 0.195$; $p \leq 0.01$) had significant and positive relationship farmers involvement in innovation dissemination. The study illuminates that the farmers level of involvement in innovation dissemination was moderate. In addition, the cassava farmers should endeavour to follow-up all the farmers they have disseminated the innovations to among members of their association in order to enhance continued usage.

Keywords: Farmers Involvement, Innovation, cassava farmers, information dissemination

INTRODUCTION

Rural dwellers have a negative mentality and consider the industry to be filthy, labour-intensive, and time-consuming; therefore, they are not drawn to pursue it (Muthomi, 2017). People always rank agriculture as their last choice when it comes to employment and job searching. Environmental concerns like insufficient acreage, bad harvests, and degraded soil were suggested as reasons why rural residents were less involved in agriculture. According to Yami, Feleke, Abdoulaye, Alene, Bamba, and Manyong (2019), rural residents' aspirations to pursue self-employment in agribusiness are significantly shaped by sociocultural factors like education level, household responsibilities, and expectations from family, communities, and the media.

According to estimates, the arable crop subsector provides over 3 million job chances. It is another labour-intensive industry that generates employment opportunities along the chain node (Groenbech, Aarons, and George, 2016). At the moment, small-scale producers account for 85 percent of the country's arable crop production (Ogunmodede, Ogunsanwo, and Manyong, 2020). The majority of these farmers are adults, with higher risk aversion and less innovative with conservative production ideas than the younger generation. Cassava production has a lot of economic possibilities, including significant yields from domestic value addition and derived income as well as government revenue. Output is anticipated to increase with advancements in cassava production techniques and varieties. Cassava production has a lot

of economic possibilities, including significant yields from domestic value addition and derived income as well as government revenue. Output is anticipated to increase with advancements in cassava production techniques and varieties.

In South America, Africa, and Asia, cassava (*Manihot utilissima* or *Manihot esculenta* Crantz), sometimes referred to as manioc or yuca, is a perennial shrub that is widely consumed and commercialized (Otálora, Garcés-Villegas, Chamorro, Palencia, Combatt and Solorzano, 2023). It is commonly recognised as the most productive crop and nutritious energy source in the tropics. Global cassava production reached over 278 million tonnes in 2018, and it has been steadily increasing in recent years (Otálora et al., 2023). Since the turn of the century, Africa has contributed the most to this production, followed by Asia and Latin America. Nigeria, Thailand, Ghana, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Brazil are among the top five producers in the world, accounting for over half of global production (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAOSTAT), 2020).

A large number of these issues can be linked to insufficient extension-to-farmer ratios that instruct the intended audience on how to use technology in agriculture to promote better farming practices, climate adaption plans, and sustainable irrigated farming. Due to these issues, agricultural production has been suppressed, which has affected the sector's GDP contribution. Additionally, as the population has grown, food imports have increased, resulting in a

decline in food sufficiency (Yami et al., 2019). The outcomes in the involvement in agricultural innovation dissemination among cassava farmers, offers a premise for designing improved agricultural practices in achieving a holistic farmers' development to reduce post-harvest losses, improved and affordable irrigation techniques, availability of ready-made market for agricultural produce, enhance human resource development among farmers among others.

For this study, this implies that, the quality of the improved agricultural innovation being disseminated as well as the frequency is very germane before achieving a desired outcome during innovation dissemination. Thus, the goal of the study is to encourage Farmer-to-Farmer Innovation Dissemination among cassava farmers in Osun State. The research was designed to describe socio economic characteristics of cassava farmers; identify innovations that cassava farmers are disseminating; relevant information on involvement of farmers in innovation disseminated; and relevant information on constraints of farmers in innovation dissemination in the study area.

One hypothesis was set in the null form for this study: there is no significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and their involvement in farmer-to-farmer innovation dissemination.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Osun State, Nigeria. The State is divided into three agricultural zones, namely, Iwo, Ife-Ijesha and Osogbo. Iwo zone has seven Local Government Areas (LGAs); Ife-Ijesha has 10 LGAs; while Osogbo has 13 LGAs. A multistage sampling procedure was used to select respondents for the study. At the first stage, based on the preponderance of cassava farmers in some LGAs: these LGAs were selected namely; Iwo LG from Iwo zone, Ife North and Ilesa West LG from Ife-Ijesa zone and Otin and Orolu LG from Osogbo zone Odo making a total of five LGAs. At the second stage, 50 percent of the registered cassava farmers across the selected LGAs were randomly selected translating to 100 from Iwo LGAs, 48 from Ife-North LGAs, 44 from Ilesa West LGAs, 18 from Odo-Otin LGAs and 109 from Orolu LGAs. In all, 319 respondents were selected for the study.

The dependent variable for this study was level of involvement in farmer-to-farmer innovation dissemination. This was measured using eight (8) activities with sixteen (16) innovations that depict total involvement. Each statement was rated on a 4-point likert scale of- never (0), occasionally (1), almost

every time (2), and every time (3). The maximum and minimum obtainable involvement score were 54 and 0 respectively. This was then then categorized into 'High', 'Moderate', and 'Low' level using equal interval. Innovations used by respondents were measured and scored 'Yes=1, No=0. In measuring constraints of farmers in innovation dissemination, ten (10) constraint variables were rated on a 4-point likert scale of not severe (0), slightly severe (1), severe (2), and highly severe (3). The maximum obtainable score was 30 while the minimum was 0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results in the Table 1 show that average age of the respondents was 47.69 ± 10.40 years. This implies that the respondents would be energetic to effectively disseminate innovations on cassava production activities to their fellow cassava farmers. This corroborates the findings of Jingjuan and Guancheng (2020) that young agricultural labour forces are productive and has a modest direct impact on agricultural productivity. Furthermore, about (68.0%) of the respondents were male which implies that there were more male respondents in innovation dissemination in the study area than their female counterparts. This finding corroborates the research of Mutenje, Kankwamba and Mangisonib (2019) who reported that females were less innovative compared to the male respondents in agricultural innovation dissemination and acceptance.

Majority (94.3%) of the farmers were married which implies that there were more married respondents and this could give them more responsibility. This is in agreement with Tijani et al. (2018) who reported that decision by married people facilitate level of involvement in cassava farming thereby reducing the constraint therein. The mean area of cassava farmland cultivated was 7.3 ± 1.5 hectares. It could also be inferred that majority of the respondents in the study area had relatively large farm size. This negates the work of Onubuogu et al. (2020) who confirmed in their work on resource use efficiency of smallholder cassava farmers in their study area that the average farm size of small holder cassava farmer was 0.97ha. In the same vein, the mean years of formal education was 11.87 ± 4.79 years. It may be inferred from the results that majority of the respondents had formal education to up to the secondary level, hence, they were literate. This is in line with the findings of Adeyongo, Chibuike, Ezike, Alabuja and Sennuga (2022), which found that Farmers in the study area are more likely to adopt new innovations due to their education, which is a key factor in their understanding of current policies and innovations.

The further finding reveals that the mean years of cassava farming experience was 15.81 ± 8.48 which means that cassava farmers were highly experienced in their cassava farming activities. This supports the work of Owoeye et al. (2021) which reported that the mean years of farming experience among farming

households in Southwest, Nigeria was 16 years. The mean annual income was $\text{₦}473,981.19 \pm \text{₦}201,310$ which mean that farmers in the study area are low-income farmers. This was consistent with the findings of Vyacheslav et al. (2020), who state that long-term agricultural production profitability is unachievable when accounting for income and production costs.

Table 1: Personal and socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Frequency (n=319)	Percentage	Standard deviation
Age			
20-40	91	28.5	47.69±10.40
41-60	194	60.8	
61-80	34	10.7	
Sex			
Male	217	68.0	
Female	102	32.0	
Marital status			
Married	298	94.3	
Single	21	5.7	
Cassava farmland cultivated (ha)			
<10	300	94.0	
10-15	13	4.1	7.32 ± 1.47
>16	6	1.9	
Years of education			
<6	67	21	
6-12	143	44.8	11.87 ± 4.79
>12	109	34.2	
Years of experience			
<10	118	37	
10-20	128	40.1	15.81±8.48
>20	73	22.9	
Income (Naira/₦)			
< 100,000.00	9	2.8	
100,000.00-500,000.00	226	70.8	₦473,981.19 ± ₦201,310.72
500,001.00-1,000,000.00	64	20.1	
>1,000,001.00	20	6.3	

Source: Field survey, 2024

Identification of various Cassava Innovations Disseminated

Result in the Table 2 shows findings on innovations disseminated. Majority (77.1%) of the respondents indicated cassava high yielding varieties innovation was disseminated while majority (67.7%) indicated use of healthy planting materials. Also, further results on cassava planting operation innovation shows that about (45.6%) of the respondents indicated do not re-use stem from the field as planting materials and majority (83.1%) of the respondents get cassava stem

from recommended sources as one of the innovations identified. In the same vein, on disease control innovation, majority (81.8%) specified recognition of important cassava diseases and majority (80.1%) stipulated growing disease tolerant varieties. On weed control methods innovation, majority (80.6%) of the respondents stipulated choosing suitable site and 82.5 percent indicated bio-control of insect pests.

Further results from the study on innovation identified on pre-harvest losses, majority (77.9%) indicated prevention of lignification, majority (72.8% and

75.1%) stipulated prevention of decaying and prevention of pests' hide-out respectively as the innovation identified. On control of post-harvest losses, majority (75.1%) subscribed to reducing losses during harvesting/picking and majority (73.1%) specified reduced losses in storing. In the same vein, on marketing innovation and value addition, majority (71.2%) of the respondents indicated sorting and grading innovation and half of the respondents (50.2%) specified packing. Also, majority (84.1% and 83.4%) indicated appropriate use of agro-chemicals and prevention of agro-chemical spillage.

The results from the study implies that majority of the cassava farmers identified various cassava innovations disseminated which may enhance their production and income generation. This result is consistent with the findings of Olanrewaju et al. (2023), who claimed that actors' relationships are intertwined with the functioning in the delivery of cassava technological information to unconnected ends and that informal networks created through interpersonal relationships have become crucial to the drive for communication of technological information needed for securing the potentials of cassava in Nigeria.

Table 2: Identification of various Cassava Innovations Disseminated (n=319)

Cassava innovations	Frequency	Percentage
Innovation on good agronomic practices		
High yielding varieties	246	77.1
Use of healthy planting materials	215	67.7
Planting operation		
Do not re-use stem from your feed as planting materials	145	45.6
Get cassava stem from recommended source	265	83.1
Disease control		
Recognition of important cassava diseases	296	81.8
Grow disease tolerant varieties	256	81.1
Cassava weed control method		
Choose suitable site (deep loamy soil free of stone)	257	80.6
Bio-control of insect pests	263	82.5
Innovation on controlling of pre-harvest losses		
Prevention of lignification	249	77.9
Prevention of decaying	231	72.8
Control of post-harvest losses		
Reduced losses in harvesting/picking	257	80.6
Reduced losses in storing	233	73.1
Marketing and value addition innovation		
Sorting and grading	277	71.2
Packing	160	50.2
Environmental protection strategy		
Appropriate use of agro-chemicals	268	84.1
Prevention of agro-chemical spillage	266	83.4

Source: Field survey, 2024

Framers Involvement in Cassava Innovations Disseminated

Results in the Figure 1 show the overall level of involvement of cassava farmers in innovation dissemination in the study area. In the overall level of involvement, this requires the combination of all the indicators used to measure the involvement score that is, 'innovation searched for, innovation disseminated/given' and 'Frequency of involvement in innovation dissemination. The results show that majority (70.5%) of the respondents indicated moderate involvement in innovation dissemination, 21.3 percent indicated high involvement while very

few (8.2%) indicated low involvement in farmer-to-farmer innovation dissemination among cassava farmers in the study area. This implies that majority (70.5%) of the cassava farmers were moderately involved in innovation dissemination and this could be as a result of the fact that infrastructures (like smart phones, regular meetings and so no) that could help enhance high involvement are adequate. Also, the farmers being committed to their own farms could affect their involvement. This is in agreement to the findings of Obinna and Agu-Aguiyi (2014) who asserted in their research that fellow farmers were highly involved in innovation dissemination.

Figure 1: Distribution of respondents based on their level of involvement in innovation dissemination

n = 319

Source: Field survey, 2024

Constraints to Innovation Dissemination among Cassava Farmers

Result in the Table 3 shows the constraints hindering to innovation dissemination among cassava farmers in the study area. These are price instability of agricultural produce (mean=1.80), high cost of agricultural input during production (mean=1.76), high perishable nature of agricultural produce (mean=1.73) and poor transportation due to inaccessible road (mean=1.72). Also, poor access to market especially during glut (mean=1.69), climate change (mean=1.63), low income generated from agriculture (mean=1.63) and inadequate access to modern equipment used for farming (mean=1.60). Furthermore, lack of awareness/access to technology

usage in agricultural production (mean=1.56) and lack of trust on innovation being disseminated among cassava farmers (mean=1.54). This implies that price instability of agricultural produce, high cost of agricultural input during production, high perishable nature of agricultural produce, poor transportation due to un-accessible road and poor access to market especially during glut were the major constraints to innovation dissemination among the cassava farmers in the study area. This conforms with the findings of Uzochukwu et al. (2021) who asserted that constraints such as poor access to credit, inadequate extension contact, high cost of labour, poor government support had a negative impact on innovation dissemination among cassava farmers.

Table 3: Constraints to Innovation Dissemination among Cassava Farmers (n=319)

Constraints variables	Ranked Mean	Mean Std. Dev
Price instability of agricultural produce	1.80	1.07
High cost of agricultural input during production	1.76	1.06
High perishable nature of agricultural produce	1.73	1.05
Poor transportation due to un-accessible road	1.72	1.01
Poor access to market especially during glut	1.69	0.97
Climate change	1.63	0.95
Low income generated from agriculture	1.63	0.94
Inadequate access to modern equipment used for farming	1.60	0.92
Lack of awareness/access to technology usage in agricultural production	1.56	0.78
Lack of trust on innovation being disseminated among cassava farmers	1.54	0.78

Source: Field survey, 2024

Hypotheses Testing

Results in the Table 4 show that household size ($r = 0.162$; ≤ 0.05), years in formal education ($r = 0.214$; ≤ 0.05), estimated annual income ($r = 0.231$; ≤ 0.01) and years in cassava farming experience ($r = 0.195$; ≤ 0.01) had significant and positive relationship with respondents' involvement in innovation dissemination at $p \leq 0.05$. However, age ($r = -0.464$; ≤ 0.05) had significant and negative relationship with the respondents' involvement in innovation dissemination. The results implies that an increase in house hold size of the respondents will enhance the

dissemination of innovation. Similarly, when there is increase in the annual income of the respondents, they will have more financial strength to carry out dissemination activities in the study area. In the same vein, the higher the year of experience the more cassava farmers would seek for more innovation to boost their farming activities. Also, the lower the age the higher the respondent's involvement in innovation dissemination. This negates the work of Torimiro et al. (2020) who asserted in their study that respondents' farm size, household size and income were negatively correlated to involvement of farmers in under-utilized indigenous vegetable production.

Table 4: Correlation analysis showing the relationship between some selected socio-economic characteristics and their involvement in innovation dissemination

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision
Household size	0.162*	0.03	S
Years of formal education	0.214*	0.02	S
Estimated annual income	0.231**	0.01	S
Years of cassava farming	0.195**	0.01	S

S = Significant

Number of respondents = 319

r = correlation co-efficient

p = probability value $p \leq 0.05$

Source: Field survey, 2024

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The respondents identified different innovation methods like good agronomic practices, Planting operation, diseases control among others. Variables like household size and estimated annual income influenced the involvement in innovation dissemination. In the same vein, majority of the respondents indicated moderate involvement in innovation dissemination. In addition, the cassava

farmers should endeavour to follow-up all the farmers they have disseminated the innovations to among members of their association in order to enhance continued usage. There should be formulation of appropriate policies on the usage of agricultural innovations by the government in a manner that would encourage the target audience to utilise it. Awareness about a particular agricultural innovation should be

adequately created for easy adoption and utilization among the farmers.

REFERENCES

Adeyongo I. L., Chibuike F., Ezike D. N., Alabuja F. O. and Sennuga S. O. (2022). Adoption of agricultural innovations among rice farmers in federal capital territory, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture Extension and Social Development*. 5(2): 30-36.

Otálora A., Garcés-Villegas V., Chamorro A., Palencia M., Combatt E. M. and Solorzano A. C. (2023). *Journal of Science with Technological Applications*. 16(96):1-10.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAOSTAT), (2020). Statistical Database. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations: Rome.
<http://faostat.fao.org/>.

Groenbech, M., Aarons, A. and George, V. (2016). Cracking Tanzania's youth employment conundrum: International Labour Organization (ILO). www.ilo.org/publns.

Jingjuan, Z. and Guancheng G. O. W. (2020): The impact of Aging Agricultural Labour Population on Farmland output: From the perspective of farmers preferences. Article ID 720618 | <https://doi.org/10.1145/2015/710618>.

Mutenje, M., Kankwamba, H., Mangisonib, J., and Kassie, M. (2019). Agricultural innovations and food security in Malawi: Gender dynamics, institutions and market implications. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 103, 240-248.

Obinna, L. O., and Agu-Aguiyi, F. N. (2014). Group dynamics and innovation dissemination among female cassava farmers in Ikwuano Local Government Area of Abia State, Nigeria. 2(10):284-290.

Ogunmodede, A. M., Ogunsanwo, M. O. and Manyong, V. (2020). Unlocking the potential of gribusiness in Africa through youth participation: An impact evaluation of N Power agro empowerment program in Nigeria. *Sustainability*, 12(5737):1-18.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su12145737>.

Olanrewaju K. O., Farinde A. J. and Adesoji S. A. (2023). Disseminating technological information for value-added production: the dual roles of cassava value chain actors in Nigeria. *Uniosun Journal of Agriculture and Renewable Resources*, UJARR, Volume 7(3): 87-101.

Onubuogu, G. C., Esiobu, N. S., Nwosu, C. S., and Okereke, C. N. (2020). Resource use efficiency of smallholder cassava farmers in Owerri Agricultural zone, Imo State, Nigeria. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 4(6): 306-318.

Owoeye, R. S., Adetule, F. S., and Sekumade, A. B. (2021): Nexus of Agricultural Commercialization among Farming Households in Southwest, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research Studies in Agricultural Sciences (IJRSAS)* 7(6):16-24. Doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.20431/2454-6224.0706003>.

Tijani, H., Tijani, B. A. and Audu, A. (2018). Socioeconomic Characteristics of Vegetable Farmers Awareness of Safety Measures in Pesticides Use in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria. *Agrosearch*, 18(1):53 – 65.

Torimiro, D. O., Adebo, O. T., Kolawole, O. D., Taiwo, F. A., Owoeye, M. O., & Ayodele, T. A. (2020). Fulani herdsman and grazing activities in southwestern Nigeria: Yoruba farm youths' perception analysis.

Uzochukwu, U. V., Mgbedike, N. G., and Chukwujekwu, O. A. (2021). Adoption of improved cassava production technologies among small-scale farmers in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Plant Sciences*, 9(4): 119-127.

Vyacheslav, Z., Kirill, Z., Vladimir, N., Lyudmila, Z., and Svetlana, R. (2020): The agricultural crops production profitability in modern conditions. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202017513008>

Yami, M., Feleke, S., Abdoulaye, T., Alene, A. D., Bamba, Z. & Manyong, V. (2019). African rural youth engagement in agribusiness: Achievements, limitations, and lessons. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(1): 1–15.